

MODELING THE KNOWLEDGE OF HIS STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF AN INTELLECTUALIZED TEST

Bazarbaeva Aygul Kuanishbaevna

Special subject teacher, Agro IT Technology of the republic of Karakalpakstan at
Tashkent university of information technologies named after Muhammed Al-
Xorezmi

Abstract. In this article, the main rules of organizing interactive education in higher education institutions and different types of classes; The organization of evaluation works based on artificial intelligence in lectures, practical lessons, seminars, laboratories and independent works has been developed. In the article, an algorithm for solving the problems of bringing the student evaluation process to a new level, that is, an algorithm for the evaluation system, was developed.

Key words: Pedagogy, teaching quality, assessment, artificial intelligence, algorithm, student, test.

The option of assessment of knowledge acquisition on the basis of artificial intelligence allows to plan the teacher's activities, to differentiate the examination, to implement systematic control, to harmonize the control of weak learners, eliminating the defects in their knowledge. The evaluation is carried out according to the following criteria: correct answers are less than 60% - 2 marks are given. Correct answers covering 60% to 70% - grade 3, covering 70% to 90% - grade 4, more than 90% grade 5. Let's describe the procedure for assessing knowledge (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Knowledge assessment procedure

In the first stage, the student answers open questions. These may be the main concepts of the course. For example, definitions. The student must select the correct option from the list of suggested options to continue the identification. If the student chooses 60% or more of the correct answers, then his knowledge is considered "satisfactory". If the test is not passed, then the knowledge is evaluated as "unsatisfactory". A student who rated the test as "satisfactory" can increase the "good" rating. A good test consists of open and closed questions. In this test, the student should demonstrate that he can use the knowledge he has acquired.

Therefore, the following types of questions are used to compose the second-level tests:

- random ordering of sequences, commands of a certain part of the program;
- prediction of the result of the execution of the given passage, additions;
- creating a block diagram of a typical program or procedure, a set of elements.

Finally, a student who tests for "good" may get "excellent." For this, the traditional, written form of passing the exam is used. Experience shows that an excellent grade, for example, can be a piece of research paper with deliberately introduced errors. In this case, the question about the number of answer options for

"satisfactory" and "good" in each question remains open. Their number should be so large that the student cannot choose the answers at random, cannot choose 60% or more correct answers. Let the complete set consist of questions and the number of questions in the test is n . Suppose that a positive score is given for test questions with six or more correct answers, then according to Bernoulli's theorem, the probability of receiving a positive score in a series of n -tests.

$$P_n = \sum_{i=6}^n C_n^i p^i q^{n-i}$$

here i - the number of "correctly guessed" answers, equal to 6, 7, 8, 9 or 10. Each of the questions can have four answers and only one of them is correct. Then the probability of guessing the correct answer in each question and correspondingly the probability of not guessing.

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